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Article

Recent Findings on the Pollution Levels in the Romanian Black Sea Ecosystem: Implications for Achieving Good Environmental Status (GES) Under the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (Directive 2008/56/EC)

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Abstract: This study provides a comprehensive evaluation of contamination levels in the Romanian Black Sea within the framework of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD). Over the course of five oceanographic expeditions between 2020 and 2022, data were gathered from 70 stations in transitional, coastal, shelf, and offshore waters of the Black Sea. Analyses were conducted on water, sediment, and biota samples for key contaminants: heavy metals (HMs), polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), and persistent organic pollutants (POPs) such as organochlorinated pesticides (OCPs) and polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs). The assessment identified contamination hotspots near riverine inputs, urban runoff, harbor activities, and industrial discharges. Offshore waters also showed measurable pollutant levels, likely from diffuse sources and atmospheric deposition. The key findings reveal the widespread contamination of HMs, PAHs, and POPs across the Romanian Black Sea, with concentrations in certain areas exceeding acceptable environmental thresholds, highlighting ongoing challenges for regional pollution management. PAHs were prevalent in both nearshore and offshore regions, while OCPs and PCBs were detected across various matrices, with significant concentrations observed in water and biota samples. The study emphasizes the importance of integrated assessments within the MSFD framework, suggesting that future evaluations should complement the “one out-all out” (OOAO) approach with multi-metric tools, to enhance the robustness of pollution status reporting. Despite improvements in some areas, contamination remains a critical challenge, requiring strengthened regulations, improved waste management, and increased regional cooperation to mitigate the ongoing risks to marine ecosystems. The findings provide valuable data for the upcoming national MSFD assessment cycle (2018–2023) and highlight the need for sustained monitoring and coordinated efforts to ensure long-term marine sustainability.

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Keywords: Black Sea; heavy metals; polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons; organochlorinated pesticides; polychlorinated biphenyls; MSFD; GES; contamination status

1. Introduction

Ocean pollution poses a significant risk to both global ecosystems and human well-being, with contamination from industrial activities, agricultural runoff, and maritime transport leading to the degradation of marine environments. The Black Sea, a partially enclosed body of water surrounded by densely industrialized and populated regions, is particularly vulnerable to these pressures [1–4]. This body of water is crucial to the region’s fisheries, biodiversity, and tourism [5], but faces persistent pollution from riverine inputs [6], urban runoff, and industrial discharges [7,8]. Ecological assessments revealed that its ecosystem has undergone significant regime shifts, characterized by changes in

its structure and function, primarily attributed to pollution and overfishing [9–12]. The cumulative effects of these contaminants not only endanger marine biodiversity but also pose a serious health risk to humans who consume contaminated seafood [13].

Previous studies [14–21] report elevated hazardous substance levels across ecosystem components; however, updated information for comprehensive regional assessments remains limited, particularly within the context of the implementation of the European Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) [22,23]. This study addresses this knowledge gap by providing an integrated assessment of contamination in the Romanian Black Sea, including new data for offshore waters, which are not covered by regular monitoring, thus contributing to ongoing efforts to achieve Good Environmental Status (GES) across European seas [22].

The Romanian Black Sea coast, facing distinct ecological and pollution pressures, is significantly impacted by river discharge, urban and industrial runoff, and seasonal tourism. Unlike widely studied open seas, the semi-enclosed Black Sea has distinct pollutant retention and distribution patterns [24–26]. This study addresses the gaps in offshore data with a focused analysis of contaminant distribution across the Romanian sector, providing insights essential for region-specific management. Our approach distinguishes itself by examining a broad spectrum of contaminants, including heavy metals (HMs), persistent organic pollutants (POPs), and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs). By analyzing these pollutants across water, sediment, and biota, we achieve a comprehensive overview of bioaccumulation and the ecosystem impact beyond typical single-matrix studies. To enhance assessment reliability, we apply a multi-indicator evaluation approach that integrates chemical and ecological indicators across multiple matrices. Using the One Out, All Out (OOAO) principle with percentile-based metrics, our approach aligns with both the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) and Water Framework Directive (WFD). This methodology, capturing cumulative impacts and subtle environmental risks, offers a model for future monitoring in similar semi-enclosed marine systems.

The Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD), formally known as Directive 2008/56/EC, was adopted by the European Union in 2008. Its main objective is to protect the marine environment across Europe to achieve a Good Environmental Status (GES) in EU marine waters by 2020 and to maintain it thereafter. The MSFD outlines an ecosystem-based approach to managing human activities that affect the marine environment, focusing on sustainable use while preventing further degradation. It establishes 11 descriptors that member states must assess and manage to protect marine health, promote biodiversity, and secure the resilience of marine ecosystems [22]. Good Environmental Status (GES), defined within the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD, Directive 2008/56/EC), represents the environmental goal for EU marine waters. Achieving GES means that the seas are ecologically diverse, clean, healthy, and productive, with their use is sustainable, ensuring the ability of ecosystems to function fully and support human needs. GES is assessed using 11 descriptors: biodiversity (D1), non-indigenous species (D2), commercial fish and shellfish (D3), food webs (D4), eutrophication (D5), seafloor integrity (D6), hydrographical conditions (D7), contaminants (D8), contaminants in seafood (D9), marine litter (D10), and energy, including underwater noise (D11); this is in order to safeguard marine environments from significant human impact while promoting sustainable use and resilience. Among them, Descriptor 8 focuses on pollutant status, ensuring contaminants have no harmful impact on the ecosystem, while Descriptor 9 addresses the state of marine ecosystems with respect to seafood safety, ensuring contaminants do not significantly affect human health. These two descriptors are particularly relevant for the Black Sea, given the historical and ongoing contamination issues in the region. Various hazardous substances have been documented to accumulate in the marine environment, potentially leading to long-term ecological damage and health risks through the food chain [27,28]. While the MSFD provides a general framework, the effectiveness of its implementation varies across European regions. The Black Sea still faces substantial challenges in monitoring, assessing, and managing pollution. The complexity of contamination sources, coupled with the Black

Sea's semi-enclosed nature, exacerbates the difficulty in mitigating these issues. Moreover, the region faces additional pressures from climate change, which can further influence contaminant distribution and impact [2,29,30].

The European Commission Decision 2017/848/EU, replacing Decision 2010/477/EU, establishes criteria and methodological standards for the good environmental status (GES) of marine waters, along with specifications and standard methods for monitoring and assessment [31]. The Contaminants Expert Group, coordinated by the Joint Research Centre (JRC), reviewed Descriptors 8 and 9. For Descriptor 8, the JRC recommends an EU-wide list of elements for GES assessment based on the Water Framework Directive (WFD), aligning GES thresholds with the WFD's Environmental Quality Standards (EQSs). National or regional criteria may be applied where EQSs are unavailable [32,33]. For Descriptor 9, the JRC suggests a similar list with GES thresholds based on the maximum levels (MAC) for contaminants in food [34].

A 2021 JRC report reviewed the 2018 GES assessments from EU Member States, including Romania [29,35]. It highlighted inconsistencies in the substances assessed, monitoring methods, and threshold values, especially in applying the WFD EQSs [31,32]. The report calls for harmonized assessment methodologies, agreed threshold values, and enhanced regional coordination, particularly for offshore waters [35,36]. The JRC also noted that many countries limit their Descriptor 9 assessments, which restricts understanding of health risks. It recommends expanding the range of contaminants and improving regional cooperation to align food safety standards [35]. To address discrepancies between D8 and D9, the JRC emphasizes harmonization and coordinated monitoring efforts across the EU to improve MSFD effectiveness [35].

Objectives of the study:

1. The quantification of hazardous substances concentrations across multiple environmental matrices (water, sediment, and biota) in the Romanian Black Sea sector, covering transitional, coastal, shelf, and offshore areas.
2. The assessment of Good Environmental Status (GES): evaluate contamination levels against the GES thresholds established under the MSFD, focusing on Descriptors 8 (pollution status) and 9 (seafood safety).
3. The identification of potential pollution sources, such as riverine inputs, industrial discharges, urban runoff, and atmospheric deposition, based on spatial patterns of contaminants in both nearshore and offshore areas.
4. The presentation of insights into the general effectiveness of the current regulatory measures and pollution control efforts, and the provision of guidance on improving monitoring and management strategies to better address marine contamination and promote long-term sustainability.

By addressing these objectives, this study provides specific and detailed data on the concentrations of key hazardous substances, including polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), heavy metals (HMs), and persistent organic pollutants (POPs), across different matrices (water, sediment, and biota). This valuable dataset is integral to the upcoming national assessment of the third cycle of MSFD reporting (2018–2023) and offers detailed insights into contamination hotspots, distribution, and the effectiveness of current regulatory measures.

This study provides a comprehensive assessment of the contamination status of the marine ecosystem, conducted within the MSFD framework from 2020 to 2022. Data on eutrophication [2], contamination, pelagic and benthic habitats were collected from 70 stations during five oceanographic expeditions, encompassing transitional, coastal, shelf, and offshore waters. While regular monitoring network extends up to 100 m in depth, this study offered us the unique opportunity to evaluate open sea waters, beyond a 200 m isobath. Our investigations focused on key contaminants, including heavy metals (HMs), polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), and persistent organic pollutants (POPs), such as organochlorinated pesticides (OCPs) and polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs), assessing their presence in relevant matrices.

The study offers crucial insights into the present state of Black Sea contamination, a regional sea facing increasing environmental and geopolitical challenges. The integrated assessment reveals areas with elevated contaminant levels, largely due to riverine inputs, urban runoff, harbor activities, and industrial discharges. Even offshore waters, which are typically less impacted, showed measurable pollutant levels, indicating the pervasive nature of contamination in the region.

This study plays a pivotal role in advancing efforts to achieve GES under the MSFD by offering valuable insights into Black Sea contamination patterns. The findings underscore the need for enhanced regulatory measures, improved waste management practices, and the stricter enforcement of pollution control regulations. This study highlights the necessity of sustained monitoring and collaborative regional efforts.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Research Area

The research was conducted in the northwestern Black Sea, within Romania's exclusive economic zone, a region characterized by unique environmental pressures and geographical features that significantly influence pollution dynamics. Five oceanographic expeditions were carried out between June 2020 and September 2022 aboard RVs "Steaua de mare" and "Mare Nigrum". The sampling campaigns were conducted during the warm seasons, in line with typical monitoring schedules and operational considerations. A comprehensive station network across all MSFD reporting regions was covered, resulting in the collection of 145 surface water samples and 116 sediment samples for contaminant analysis. The sediment sampling stations coincided with those of the water samples (Figure 1a), with the exception of stations deeper than 500 m. Additionally, 18 mollusk samples (*Mytilus galloprovincialis*, *Rapana venosa*) were collected from coastal and shelf areas during 2020–2022 (Figure 1b).

Figure 1. Cont.

Figure 1. (a) Locations of water and sediment sampling stations, 2020–2022. (b) Map of mollusk sampling stations, 2020–2022.

The study region was subdivided into four designated marine reporting units (MRUs) (Figure 2):

Figure 2. The four designated marine reporting units (MRUs).

Transitional waters (BLK_RO_RG_TT03): From the baseline to the 29 m isobath.

Coastal waters (BLK_RO_RG_CT): From the baseline to the 29 m isobath.

Shelf waters (BLK_RO_RG_MT01): From the 30 m isobath to the 200 m isobath.

Offshore waters (BLK_RO_RG_MT02): Beyond the 200 m isobath.

The Romanian Black Sea sector (244 km coastline, comprising 6% of the Black Sea’s total) faces significant environmental pressures due to a confluence of factors. The area

is influenced by the Danube River's discharge in the north and industrialized urban centers in the south, while a surge in summer tourism further complicates matters. Other major rivers, like the Dniester, Dnieper, Don, and Bug, also have a substantial impact on the northwestern region. The southern coast is defined by major activities including wastewater treatment, beach restoration, maritime transportation, fishing, and oil and gas extraction [4,37]. While sewage treatment plants have faced challenges, improvements were noted in 2018 due to upgrades and expansions [2]. The major ports of Constanta, Mangalia, and Midia are crucial for maritime transport. Offshore oil and gas exploration and production have been significant since the 1970s, contributing 8% of Romania's oil and gas output [4]. Environmental pressures primarily stem from shipping, coastal defense, and construction activities [7]. Shipping is the most significant contributor, causing pollution and marine litter. Coastal defense and flood protection measures disrupt natural sediment dynamics, while dredging and offshore construction lead to habitat loss and biodiversity changes [2,4,7].

The geographical region offers valuable insights into the broader pollution dynamics of the Black Sea due to its varied environmental pressures. The interplay of riverine inputs and intense industrial and maritime activities along the coast make this sector particularly significant for studying pollutant distribution patterns [38]. The mix of pollutants from urban, agricultural, and industrial sources, including contaminants such as heavy metals, organic compounds, and nutrients, combined with seasonal tourism, contributes to a complex contamination landscape [4]. This area's semi-enclosed nature further exacerbates pollutant retention and distribution, making it an ideal site for understanding how contaminants behave in both coastal and offshore environments. Eutrophication, a process driven by excessive nutrient inputs that can lead to harmful algal blooms and oxygen depletion, is also a significant concern in this region due to agricultural runoff and urban wastewater discharges [2,39]. The regional characteristics provide a microcosm for assessing pollution dynamics across the wider Black Sea ecosystem.

2.2. Sample Collection and Initial Preparation Methods

Water Sampling: Surface water samples were collected using Niskin bottles, which are specifically designed to prevent contamination during collection. All samples were taken from the uppermost layer (0–1 m) across various locations, ensuring consistency in the sampling depth. This method ensures that the data reflect the surface water layer's quality, which is most affected by atmospheric interactions, runoff, and human activities. Immediately after collection, the samples were stored at 4–8 °C to preserve their integrity for further analysis [40].

Sediment Sampling: Surface sediments were collected using a Van Veen grab sampler, which is ideal for retrieving undisturbed sediment samples from the top 2–5 cm layer, which represents recent pollutant deposition [41]. The design of the grab minimizes disturbance to the sediment profile, ensuring that the surface layer remains intact, and that the data accurately reflect current contamination levels. After collection, the samples were stored at –20 °C.

Mollusk Sampling: Mollusks (*Mytilus galloprovincialis* and *Rapana venosa*) were collected using a biological dredge. The dredge method ensures that multiple individuals are gathered from each sampling location, allowing for composite samples (5–10 individuals) that are representative of the area [42]. The mollusks were harvested from both coastal and shelf waters, providing a comprehensive view of contaminant levels across different habitats. Following collection, the mollusks were promptly stored in freezer boxes to maintain sample integrity before further laboratory analysis.

Sampling efforts focused on surface water, surface sediment, and mollusks, with no depth-specific adjustments required for water or sediment. The sampling strategy considered transitional, coastal, shelf and offshore areas, to capture spatial variations in contamination levels. Consistent methods were used across locations to ensure the comparability of results.

In the laboratory, sediments and mollusks (whole soft tissue) were subjected to lyophilization, resulting in the complete removal of water content. The freeze-dried samples were subsequently analyzed for inorganic and organic pollutants. The sediments were sieved to eliminate coarse fragments larger than 0.5 mm. The dried samples were homogenized using an electric grinder [40–42].

2.3. Analytical Techniques

2.3.1. Heavy Metals (HMs)

The concentrations of copper (Cu), cadmium (Cd), lead (Pb), nickel (Ni), and chromium (Cr) in seawater were measured from unfiltered, acidified water samples (acidified to pH 2 using ultrapure HNO₃). For the analysis of heavy metals (HMs) in sediment and biological tissues, approximately 0.05–0.5 g of dried material was digested with 10 mL of concentrated HNO₃ inside sealed Teflon vessels on a hot plate at 120 °C. The resulting solution was diluted to 100 mL with deionized water (18.2 MΩ·cm, Millipore, Burlington, MA, USA). The HMs concentrations were determined using a High-Resolution Continuum Source Atomic Absorption Spectrometer (HR-CS ContrAA 800 G, Analytik Jena, Jena, Germany). Calibration standards were prepared from Merck stock solutions for each element with the following concentration ranges: 0–50 µg/L for Cu and Ni, 0–10 µg/L for Cd, 0–25 µg/L for Pb, and 0–50 µg/L for Cr. Each sample was tested in triplicate, and the average value was recorded. The detection limits for the HMs varied between 0.001 and 0.01 µg/L, depending on the element. Standardized protocols were employed throughout the analytical procedures to ensure accuracy and consistency [40,41,43]. The HMs concentrations in seawater are reported in µg/L, while in sediments they are expressed as µg/g dry weight (dw), and in biological tissues as µg/g tissue dry weight (dw).

2.3.2. Persistent Organic Pollutants (POPs): Organochlorinated Pesticides (OCPs) and Polychlorinated Biphenyls (PCBs), and Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAHs) Extraction in Biota

For the analysis of POPs, approximately 2 g of biota sample was extracted using a microwave-assisted method with an acetone/hexane (1:1) mixture. The internal standard, 2,4,5-Trichlorobiphenyl, was added to the samples to assess the recovery efficiency throughout the analytical process. Lipids were removed by adding 10 mL of concentrated H₂SO₄, followed by cleanup with copper and fractionation using a florisil column. The samples were then concentrated under a nitrogen stream in a water bath and analyzed using GC-ECD [44].

PAH compounds were extracted from approximately 2 g of freeze-dried tissues using the Soxhlet extraction method. The internal standard, 9,10-dihydroanthracene, was added to assess the recovery efficiency of the analytical procedure. Samples were extracted for 8 h with 250 mL of methanol using the Soxhlet apparatus. The resulting extracts were saponified by adding 20 mL of 0.7 M KOH and 30 mL of water, followed by reflux for 2 h. The PAH-containing fraction was then concentrated under a gentle nitrogen stream to a final volume of 1 mL and analyzed by GC-MS. [44].

2.3.3. POPs' and PAHs' Extraction in Seawater and Sediments

Seawater samples were extracted using a hexane/dichloromethane (3:1) mixture in a funnel, while sediment samples underwent microwave extraction. Following extraction, cleanup was performed with copper, and fractionation was conducted using a florisil column for OCPs and an alumina/silica column for PAHs. The samples were then concentrated under a nitrogen stream in a water bath and analyzed by GC-ECD for OCPs and GC-MS for PAHs. Internal standards, namely 2,4,5-Trichlorobiphenyl for POPs and 9,10-dihydroanthracene for PAHs, were added to assess the recovery efficiency of the analytical procedures [44].

2.3.4. Gas Chromatographic Analyses of POPs and PAHs

For the analysis of OCPs and PCBs, concentrated extracts were examined using a Perkin Elmer Clarus 500 gas chromatograph equipped with an electron capture detector (GC/ECD) (PerkinElmer Inc., Waltham, MA, USA). The quantification of specific OCPs and PCBs was performed by comparing the peak areas of the samples to those of known standards. Calibration curves for GC-ECD were generated using individual standards for nine OCPs (Hexachlorobenzene, Lindane, Heptachlor, Aldrin, Dieldrin, Endrin, p,p'DDE, p,p'DDD, and p,p'DDT) and 7 PCBs (PCB 28, PCB 52, PCB 101, PCB 118, PCB 138, PCB 152, and PCB 180), with concentrations ranging between 1000 and 5000 µg/mL dissolved in methanol.

For PAH analysis, the concentrated extract was examined using a Perkin Elmer Clarus 690 system with gas chromatography–mass spectrometry (GC/MS) (PerkinElmer Inc., Waltham, MA, USA). A standard mixture containing the 16 priority PAHs—naphthalene (Na), acenaphthylene (Ac), acenaphthene (Ace), fluorene (Flu), anthracene (An), phenanthrene (Ph), fluoranthene (Fln), pyrene (Pyr), benzo[a]anthracene (BaA), chrysene (Chr), benzo[a]pyrene (BaP), benzo[b]fluoranthene (BbF), benzo[k]fluoranthene (BkF), benzo[g,h,i]perylene (BghiP), indeno [1,2,3-cd]pyrene (IP), and dibenzo[a,h]anthracene (DaA)—dissolved in toluene at individual concentrations of 100 µg/mL was used to calibrate the GC-MS [44].

The data were interpreted using MS Excel 365, Statistica (TIBCO Software Version 14.0.1.25) [45], Ocean Data View (ODV) version 5.1.7 [46] and ArcGIS Desktop 10.7 software [47]. Distribution maps were created using IDW interpolation in ArcGIS.

2.4. Methodology for Contamination Status Assessment

Good Environmental Status (GES) has been defined based on Criterion D8C1 (Descriptor 8) and Criterion D9C1 (Descriptor 9). For these criteria, GES, associated indicators, and environmental objectives have been defined (Table 1).

The marine assessment areas, identified as reported to the European Environment Agency (EEA), WISE-MARINE (<https://sdi.eea.europa.eu/catalogue/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/a14375b6-13fa-44d2-9e01-f8bee5954dbb>, accessed on 29 September 2024), are designated with the following codes: transitional waters—BLK_RO_RG_TT03, coastal waters—BLK_RO_RG_CT, marine shelf area—BLK_RO_RG_MT01 and offshore waters—BLK_RO_RG_MT02 (Descriptor 8), respectively (Descriptor 9).

The evaluation of Descriptor 8 focused on the contaminant concentrations in water and sediment samples collected between 2020 and 2022. Data were centralized, processed, statistically analyzed, and compared to the proposed threshold values for GES [48]. The definition of GES for Descriptor 8 involved, starting with the previous assessment in the framework of MSFD reporting, a comprehensive review of existing methodologies at the national, regional, and European levels [29]. An appropriate methodology was selected for the analyzed group of contaminants, and background values and threshold values were carefully assessed [49].

For sediments, given the absence of European legislation specifying contaminant threshold values, we selected established benchmarks, such as Effect Range Low levels (ERL) [50,51], which are widely used to assess sediment quality and the potential ecological risks associated with contaminant levels in marine and freshwater environments [49,51–53]. The Effect Range Low (ERL), developed by Long and Morgan (1991) under the US Environmental Protection Agency (US EPA) [50], is a sediment quality guideline used to evaluate the potential ecological effects of contaminant concentrations in sediments. It represents the lower threshold within a range of contaminant concentrations where adverse biological effects are rarely observed.

ERL indicates a concentration below which adverse effects on marine life are unlikely to occur, making it a conservative benchmark to protect ecosystems [53]. Effect Range Median (ERM), often used alongside ERL, represents a higher threshold where adverse effects are more frequently observed [51]. ERL values are derived from long-term data, linking contaminant concentrations to the observed biological effects [50]. They provide an impor-

tant tool for sediment quality assessment, allowing researchers to interpret whether the measured concentrations of specific contaminants (e.g., heavy metals, organic pollutants) are likely to pose ecological risks.

In this study, ERL values were used to determine appropriate threshold concentrations for contaminants in sediments, especially in the absence of specific European legislation. When the contaminant concentrations in sediments exceed ERL values, they may indicate a potential risk to benthic organisms, but values below ERL values generally suggest that the sediment is safe for marine life [51,53]. ERL values provide a scientifically validated foundation for determining threshold values in sediment contamination assessments. By applying these widely recognized thresholds [52], we ensure that the risk of harmful effects on marine ecosystems is minimized. For contaminants without specific European or national standards, ERL values serve as an effective and precautionary guideline for assessing sediment quality and maintaining compliance with the goals of the MSFD [49].

This study aligns with European environmental regulations, specifically Directive 2013/39/EU (Priority Substances Directive), which establishes Environmental Quality Standards (EQS) for priority substances in surface waters [36]. Directive 2013/39/EU is an important amendment to the Water Framework Directive (WFD, Directive 2000/60/EC) [33]. The WFD was adopted by the European Union in 2000, and its primary goal is to establish a comprehensive framework for the protection and sustainable management of inland surface waters, transitional waters, coastal waters, and groundwater across EU member states. It requires that all European waters achieve “good status” by setting ecological and chemical standards for water bodies, targeting pollution reduction, and promoting sustainable water use [33]. Directive 2013/39/EU focuses on setting specific Environmental Quality Standards (EQSs) for priority substances in surface waters, addressing pollutants that pose significant risks to aquatic environments and human health. By establishing and updating the threshold limits for pollutants such as heavy metals and organic compounds [36], it plays a crucial role in harmonizing water quality goals across the WFD and MSFD. It aims to reduce harmful substances in both freshwater and marine environments, aiding in the achievement of Good Ecological Status under the WFD [33] and Good Environmental Status under the MSFD [22].

Most pollutants evaluated in this research are among the substances regulated under this directive: cadmium, lead, nickel, anthracene, naphthalene, fluoranthene, benzo(a)pyrene, benzo(b)fluoranthene, benzo(k)fluoranthene, benzo(g,h,i)perylene, HCB, lindane, heptachlor, the sum of cyclodiene pesticides, p,p' DDT, and total DDT. By comparing the measured concentrations to the Maximum Allowable Concentration (MAC-EQS) values set by the directive, we aim to assess the potential ecological risks posed by short-term contamination events in the seawater. This approach ensures that our findings are directly relevant to European regulatory frameworks and can inform effective environmental management strategies [22,36].

Descriptor 9 assessed the levels of contaminants in edible seafood. The criterion used, D9C1, evaluated whether these levels exceeded the established Maximum Admissible Concentration (MAC) for organisms caught in the wild. Data available between 2020 and 2022 on the contaminant concentrations in commercially important mollusk species (*Mytilus galloprovincialis* and *Rapana venosa*), harvested from coastal waters and the shelf zone, were analyzed and compared to target values for GES. The definition of GES was based on the MACs imposed by the current European or national legislation for the following substances: Cd, Pb, Sum of PCB28, PCB52, PCB101, PCB138, PCB153 and PCB180 (total ICES-6), OCPs (HCB, lindane, aldrin, endrin, dieldrin, p,p'DDE, p,p' DDD, p,p' DDT), Benzo(a)Pyrene, and the sum of PAHs (Benzo(a)Pyrene, (Benzo(a)anthracene, Benzo(b)fluoranthene and Chrysene) [34,54].

To determine if the marine environment has a Good Environmental Status (GES), the methodology requires that 75% of the concentrations for an individual compound measured over the evaluation period in each matrix are below threshold values [22,29,31]. The following formula illustrates how the exceedance rate is calculated for GES determination:

$$\text{Exceedance Rate(\%)} = \frac{N_{\text{total}}}{N_{\text{exceedances}}} \times 100$$

where $N_{\text{exceedances}}$ is the number of samples exceeding the EQS, and N_{total} is the total number of samples analyzed. Exceedance rates provide insight into the frequency and scale of contaminant breaches, highlighting areas of potential environmental concern. A maximum exceedance rate of 25% is accepted to ensure that most of the marine environment is not contaminated beyond acceptable levels.

Using the 75th percentile allows for some natural variation in pollutant concentrations while still ensuring that most of the environment is protected. It provides a safety margin to account for factors like seasonal variations, localized pollution events, or analytical uncertainties. Achieving GES for a specific pollutant does not imply zero contamination. It indicates that the overall ecosystem is in good condition, but it does not mean that there are no contaminants present, since a maximum of 25% of EQSs surpassing values are considered acceptable. Even small exceedances can have impacts, considering that the effects of contaminants can be cumulative, and even low levels over time can have adverse effects on the ecosystem [55].

Following the evaluation for each individual compound, the “One Out, All Out” (OOAO) approach was further used in contamination assessment. The One Out, All Out (OOAO) method is a precautionary approach used in environmental assessments under frameworks like the WFD and MSFD [33,56]. This method dictates that if any single element or contaminant within an assessment area (such as a marine reporting unit) fails to meet its threshold or target level, the entire area is classified as failing to achieve Good Environmental Status (GES). OOAO is designed to ensure stringent environmental protection by identifying even minor exceedances that could signal potential ecological risks. However, while effective in highlighting problem areas, OOAO is sometimes critiqued for its conservative nature, as it may not account for the overall ecological health if only one component is slightly out of compliance [56,57].

Our methodology for contamination status assessment essentially states that if one or more substances within a specific group is non-GES, the entire group is considered not achieving GES. The OOAO principle is applied sequentially, starting from individual pollutants, groups of compounds and matrices, and progressing to marine reporting units (MRUs). In other words, if the 75th percentile of contaminant concentrations exceeds the threshold value at any level, the component (compound, group, or matrix) and potentially the entire marine reporting unit is considered contaminated (non-GES) [29].

Table 1. Summary of criteria, indicators, and thresholds used for national GES evaluation—Descriptors 8 and 9.

Criteria	Indicators	GES Definition	Threshold Values
<p>D8C1: In coastal and territorial waters, contaminant concentrations must adhere to the following thresholds: (a) For contaminants listed in point 1(a) of the criteria elements, the levels specified by Directive 2000/60/EC; (b) If contaminants from point (a) are detected in a matrix without an established value under the Directive, Member States will set the concentration through regional or sub-regional cooperation; (c) For additional contaminants noted in point 1(b), Member States will determine concentration limits for specific matrices (water, sediment, or biota) that may pose pollution risks, taking into account their significance within and beyond coastal and territorial waters [31].</p>	<p>HMs, POPs, PAHs concentrations in seawater (surface), and sediments [29].</p>	<p>Concentrations of the relevant contaminants detected in suitable matrices (water, sediment) are either below levels that could cause negative effects or show a declining trend [22] The 75th percentile of contaminants concentrations per Marine Reporting Unit (MRU) and matrix should not exceed the target values during the evaluation period [29].</p>	<p>The threshold values selected in accordance with Directive 2000/60/EC (EQS) [33,36] or based on the national or regional values [49,51–54]</p>

Table 1. Cont.

Criteria	Indicators	GES Definition	Threshold Values
D9C1: The contaminant levels in edible tissues of wild-caught seafood (including fish, crustaceans, mollusks, echinoderms, seaweed) must not exceed: (a) The maximum levels specified in EC Regulation for listed contaminants [34], which serve as the threshold values for this Decision; (b) For additional contaminants not covered by EC Regulation, threshold values determined by Member States through regional or sub-regional cooperation [31].	Cd and Pb in mollusks Sum of PCB28, PCB52, PCB101, PCB138, PCB153 and PCB180 (total ICES-6) in mollusks OCPs (HCB, lindan, aldrin, endrin, dieldrin, p,p' DDE, p,p' DDD, p,p' DDT) in mollusks Benzo(a)Pyrene, Sum of PAHs (Benzo(a)Pyrene, (Benzo(a)anthracene, Benzo(b)fluoranthene and Chrysene) in mollusks	Contaminants levels in mollusks should be below MACs set out by European [34] and national legislation [58] for human consumption. The 75th percentile of contaminant concentrations in mollusks is below the regulated levels throughout the evaluation period [29].	MACs from European [34] or national legislation [58]

3. Results

3.1. Descriptor 8: Contaminant Assessment

The aim of the assessment was to analyze the presence and levels of harmful contaminants in marine waters and sediments. By analyzing data from various locations and comparing it to established thresholds, the study assessed the environmental status of each marine reporting unit (MRU) based on the contaminant concentration levels. The specific contaminants of interest were HMs, POPs (OCPs and PCBs), and PAHs. For each individual compound within these categories, data were analyzed to compare the measured concentrations with the established threshold values that define good ecological status. The results were presented for each pollutant category, marine reporting unit, and matrix (water and sediment). A key statistical parameter used in the assessment was the 75th percentile, which represents the value below which 75% of the data fall. This parameter served as a benchmark to evaluate the overall level of contamination in each region and matrix (GES, non-GES).

3.1.1. Transitional Waters—BLK-RO-RG-TT03

The data presented in Table 2 are based on 20 seawater and 19 sediments samples collected between 2020 and 2022. The 75th percentile was calculated by sorting the data and selecting the value below which 75% of the results fall, ensuring that natural variability is accounted for. GES is achieved when the 75th percentile is below the EQS, meaning that exceedance rates are less than 25%. The percentage of samples exceeding threshold values (EQS or ERL) was calculated to assess the frequency of contamination above acceptable levels, providing insight into potential environmental risks.

Persistent Organic Pollutants (POPs)

Waters receiving significant freshwater input from the Danube River were found to be contaminated with persistent organic pollutants. In 14% to 72% of the water samples analyzed, the levels of these pollutants exceeded safe limits for a healthy ecosystem (Figure 3). However, hexachlorobenzene and heptachlor were exceptions, meeting the standards for GES. In sediments, most pollutants remained within safe limits, except for lindane, resulting in a poor overall environmental status (non-GES) for both the water and sediment regarding POPs. This is due to the application of the “one out, all out” (OOAO) approach, meaning that if even one compound exceeds safe limits, the entire MRU is classified as being in poor condition (Table 2).

Figure 3. Exceedances of the threshold values for OCPs in the transitional waters, 2020–2022.

It is important to mention that the heptachlor detection limit (LOD 0.003 µg/L) exceeds the regulatory threshold for seawater [36], which introduces some uncertainty. This discrepancy arises from the technical limitations of the analytical method, where the LOD surpasses the threshold value. Although the detectable concentrations comply with GES criteria (75% of values being close to LOD) in some cases, concentrations below the LOD remain indeterminate. This is a common challenge in environmental assessments, especially for this compound [59].

Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAHs)

The levels of PAHs in the Danube-impacted waters were found to be low. Only a very small number of samples showed PAH concentrations that exceeded the safe limits for a healthy ecosystem (9% for anthracene and 1% for benzo(k)fluoranthene and benzo(g,h,i)perilen). As a result, both the water and sediment samples were regarded as being in good environmental condition regarding PAHs (Table 2).

Heavy Metals (HMs)

The HMs levels in transitional waters were generally below the EQS, indicating good ecological status. Copper (4%) and lead (8%) had some exceedances, but the percentages were relatively low. This suggests that while there is some metal contamination in the water, it is not at levels that significantly threaten the ecosystem. The situation was more concerning for sediment. Nickel significantly exceeded the EQS in many samples (67%), leading to a non-GES status. Copper and lead also had exceedances, but to a lesser extent (copper 24% and lead 17%) (Table 2).

Previous studies reported that nickel (Ni) concentrations in the north-western Black Sea sediments ranged from 1 to 207 µg/g, with an average of 66.4 µg/g [60–62]. In some areas, these concentrations exceeded the Effect Range Low (ERL) value [61]. Studies indicate that Ni shows a strong geochemical association with Fe₂O₃, reflecting its natural origin from regional lithology [60,61]. Furthermore, its correlation with total organic carbon (TOC) suggests the influence of terrigenous material and biogenic sources, where organic matter can adsorb and concentrate metals [61–63]. While these elevated Ni levels surpass Environmental Quality Standards (EQSs), they are consistent with the naturally high background levels of the Black Sea, as demonstrated through normalization using elements such as Rb or Fe [60,61]. Consequently, while Ni concentrations exceed regulatory thresholds, this primarily reflects natural geochemical inputs rather than anthropogenic contamination [61–63]. Further studies are recommended to better differentiate between natural and anthropogenic sources of heavy metals in sediments [64–67].

The integration of the results for each compound within contaminant groups, using OOA, highlighted both a poor ecological status (non-GES) for some contaminant groups/matrices and a good ecological status (GES) for other contaminant groups/matrices.

Through the integration of all the results together, with all contaminant groups (HMs, POPs, PAHs) and matrices, the overall ecological status of the transitional waters MRU-BLK-RO-RG-TT03 was found to be poor (non-GES), based on the OOA principle (Table 3). The OOA principle means that if even one contaminant group within a specific matrix (like water or sediment) is found to have a poor status, then the overall ecological status is considered non-GES. In other words, if any part of the system is unhealthy, the whole is considered unhealthy. Overall, the conclusion is that despite some individual contaminant groups having good ecological status, the overall health of the transitional water area is poor due to the presence of at least one contaminant group with a non-GES status.

Table 2. Status of the transitional waters, 2020–2022 (POPs, PAHs, HMs).

Matrix	Compound	75th Percentile	Threshold Value	Environmental Status per Compound
Water (µg/L)	HCB	0.018	0.05	GES
	Lindane	1.603	0.02	Non-GES
	Heptaclor *	0.003	0.00003	GES
	Sum of cyclodiene pesticides	3.623	0.005	Non-GES
	p,p'DDT	2.000	0.01	
	DDT total	6.751	0.025	
	Naphthalene	0.0201	130	GES
	Anthracene	0.0001	0.1	
	Fluoranthene	0.0001	0.12	
	Benzo(a)pyrene	0.0001	0.027	
	Benzo(b)fluoranthene	0.0001	0.017	
	Benzo(k)fluoranthene	0.0001	0.017	
	Benzo(g,h,i)perylene	0.0001	0.00082	
	Copper	14.08	30	GES
	Cadmium	0.32	1.5	
	Lead	2.03	14	
	Nickel	4.30	34	
Chromium	5.85	100		
Sediment (POPs and PAHs µg/kg dry weight; HMs µg/g dry weight)	HCB	1.0981	20	GES
	Lindane	3.2295	3	Non-GES
	Dieldrin	0.0178	2	GES
	p,p'DDE	0.0020	2.2	
	PCB 28	0.0212	1.7	
	PCB 52	0.0348	2.7	
	PCB 101	0.0060	3	
	PCB 118	0.0040	0.6	
	PCB 153	0.0090	40	
	PCB 138	0.0070	7.9	
PCB 180	0.0030	12		

Table 2. Cont.

Matrix	Compound	75th Percentile	Threshold Value	Environmental Status per Compound
Sediment (POPs and PAHs µg/kg dry weight; HMs µg/g dry weight)	Naphthalene	10.15	160	GES
	Acenaphthene	0.1	16	
	Phenanthrene	17.77	240	
	Anthracene	0.1	85	
	Fluoranthene	27.57	600	
	Pyrene	30	665	
	Benzo[a] anthracene	9.939	261	
	Chrysene	9.322	384	
	Benzo[a]pyrene	29.10	430	
	Benzo(g,h,i)perylene	0.1	85	
	Indeno(1,2,3-c,d)pyrene	0.1	240	
	Total ΣHAP	158.644	1000	
	Copper	40.70	40	GES
	Cadmium	0.41	1.2	
	Lead	45.59	47	Non-GES
Nickel	57.99	35		
Chromium	51.46	81	GES	

* The limit of detection (LOD) for heptachlor is higher than the threshold value stipulated by Directive 39/2013. The percentile refers to the exceedances of LOD. Green—GES achieved, red—GES not achieved.

Table 3. Overall assessment of environmental status in the transitional waters, 2020–2022.

MRU	Matrix	Group of Compounds	Environmental Status per Group of Contaminants	Environmental Status for the Assessment Area
Transitional waters BLK-RO-RG-TT03	Water	POPs	Non-GES	Non-GES
		PAHs	GES	
		HM	GES	
	Sediment	POPs	Non-GES	
		PAHs	GES	
		HMs	Non-GES	

Green—GES achieved, red—GES not achieved.

3.1.2. Coastal Waters—BLK-RO-RG-CT

The data presented in Table 4 are based on 37 seawater and 33 sediments samples collected between 2020 and 2022. The 75th percentile was calculated by sorting the data and selecting the value below which 75% of the results fall, ensuring that natural variability is accounted for. GES is achieved when the 75th percentile is below the EQSs, meaning that exceedance rates are less than 25%. The percentage of samples exceeding threshold values (EQS or ERL) was calculated to assess the frequency of contamination above acceptable levels, providing insight into potential environmental risks.

Table 4. Status of the coastal waters, 2020–2022 (POPs, PAHs, HMs).

Matrix	Compound	Percentile 75th	Threshold Value	Environmental Status per Compound
Water (µg/L)	HCB	0.004	0.05	GES
	Lindane	1.749	0.02	Non-GES
	Heptachlor *	0.003	0.00003	GES

Table 4. Cont.

Matrix	Compound	Percentile 75th	Threshold Value	Environmental Status per Compound
Water ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Sum of cyclodiene pesticides	1.992	0.005	Non-GES
	p,p' DDT	1.507	0.01	
	DDT total	7.143	0.025	
	Naphthalene	0.022	130	GES
	Anthracene	0.0001	0.1	
	Fluoranthene	0.0001	0.12	
	Benzo(a)pyrene	0.0001	0.027	
	Benzo(b)fluoranthene	0.0001	0.017	
	Benzo(k)fluoranthene	0.0001	0.017	
	Benzo(g,h,i)perylene	0.0001	0.00082	GES
	Copper	11.05	30	
	Cadmium	0.08	1.5	
	Lead	1.74	14	
	Nickel	2.34	34	
Chromium	4.71	100	GES	
Sediment (POPs and PAHs $\mu\text{g/kg}$ dry weight; HMs $\mu\text{g/g}$ dry weight)	HCB	0.8819		20
	Lindane	2.1794		3
	Dieldrin	0.0034		2
	p,p' DDE	0.0020		2.2
	PCB 28	0.0115		1.7
	PCB 52	0.0266		2.7
	PCB 101	0.0060		3
	PCB 118	0.0040		0.6
	PCB 153	0.0090		40
	PCB 138	0.0070		7.9
	PCB 180	0.0030		12
	Naphthalene	1.4577		160
	Acenaphthene	0.1		16
	Phenanthrene	16.4169	240	
	Anthracene	0.1	85	
	Fluoranthene	14.5104	600	
	Pyrene	13.6701	665	
	Benzo[a] anthracene	8.2683	261	
	Chrysene	7.0990	384	
	Benzo[a]pyrene	24.5123	430	
	Benzo(g,h,i)perylene	0.1	85	
	Indeno(1,2,3-c,d)pyrene	3.0244	240	
	Total Σ HAP	126.313	1000	
	Copper	17.01	40	GES
Cadmium	0.22	1.2		
Lead	14.10	47		
Nickel	30.02	35		
Chromium	34.10	81		

* The limit of detection (LoD) for heptachlor is higher than the threshold value stipulated by Directive 39/2013. The percentile refers to the exceedances of LoD. Green—GES achieved, red—GES not achieved.

Persistent Organic Pollutants (POPs)

In 11–89% of samples, most POP concentrations in coastal waters exceeded the GES thresholds (Figure 4). Hexachlorobenzene (HCB) and heptachlor were the only compounds that met the criteria for GES. Consequently, the water quality assessment resulted in a non-GES status (Table 4).

Figure 4. Exceedances of the threshold values for OCPs in coastal waters, 2020–2022.

In sediments, all compounds were within the range for GES, and this matrix was therefore classified as having a good status.

Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAHs)

These compounds were found to be at rather low levels in the coastal waters. None of the samples exceeded the threshold values, except benzo(g,h,i)perilen (4%). Both the water and the sediment samples were determined to have good ecological status, based on the 75th percentile values of the monitoring data (Table 4). This means that the overall environmental condition of the coastal area, as assessed by PAHs, was considered good (GES).

Heavy Metals (HMs)

The 75th percentile concentrations for all HMs in both the water and sediment matrices were below the Environmental Quality Standards (EQSs), which means that GES is achieved, but there are still some instances of exceedances observed. In water, only copper (Cu) showed exceedances in 3% of samples; meanwhile, in sediment, exceedances were observed for copper (Cu) and lead (Pb) in 3%, and nickel (Ni) in 21% of samples (Table 4). Despite these exceedances, which were maintained below 25% (GES threshold), the ecological status for all metals in the coastal area is still classified as good (GES). This indicates that while most samples are within safe limits, isolated instances of elevated HM concentrations do occur.

By combining the results for elements within the contaminant group, using the OAO principle, both a poor and good ecological status were identified for various contaminant groups or matrices. While some individual pollutant groups exhibited good ecological status, the presence of contaminants in other groups led to a negative overall assessment. Through the integration of results obtained for all contaminant groups and matrices, using the one-out-all-out (OOAO) principle, an overall poor ecological status (non-GES) was determined for the evaluated coastal area (Table 5). This conclusion is reached by applying the one-out-all-out principle, which states that if one component of a system fails, the entire system is considered to have failed. In this case, even though some pollutant groups were within acceptable limits, the presence of contaminants in others compromised the overall water quality.

Table 5. Assessment of the environmental status for coastal area, 2020–2022.

MRU	Matrix	Group of Compounds	Environmental Status per Group of Contaminants	Environmental Status for MRU
Coastal waters BLK-RO-RG-CT	Water	POPs	GES	Non-GES
		PAHs		
		HMs		
	Sediment	POPs		
		PAHs		
		HMs		

Green—GES achieved, red—GES not achieved.

3.1.3. Shelf Waters (BLK_RO_RG_MT01)

The data presented in Table 6 are based on 70 seawater and 61 sediment samples collected between 2020 and 2022. The 75th percentile was calculated by sorting the data and selecting the value below which 75% of the results fall, ensuring that natural variability is accounted for. GES is achieved when the 75th percentile is below the EQS, meaning that exceedance rates are less than 25%. The percentage of samples exceeding threshold values (EQS or ERL) was calculated to assess the frequency of contamination above acceptable levels, providing insight into potential environmental risks.

Table 6. Status of the shelf marine waters, 2020–2022 (POPs, PAHs, HMs).

Matrix	Compound	Percentile 75th	Threshold Value	Environmental Status per Compound
Water (µg/L)	HCB	0.024	0.05	GES
	Lindane	4.958	0.02	Non-GES
	Heptaclor *	0.342	0.00003	
	Sum of cyclodiene pesticides	5.374	0.005	
	p,p'DDT	0.465	0.01	
	DDT total	6.501	0.025	
	Naphthalene	0.0172	130	
	Anthracene	0.0001	0.1	GES
	Fluoranthene	0.0001	0.12	
	Benzo(a)pyrene	0.0001	0.027	
	Benzo(b)fluoranthene	0.0001	0.017	
	Benzo(k) fluoranthene	0.0001	0.017	
	Benzo(g,h,i)perylene	0.0001	0.00082	
	Copper	8.77	30	GES
	Cadmium	0.04	1.5	
Lead	1.78	14		
Nickel	3.05	34		
Chromium	23.24	100		
Sediment (POPs and PAHs µg/kg dry weight; HMs µg/g dry weight)	HCB	0.3694	20	GES
	Lindane	0.5880	3	
	Dieldrin	0.1143	2	
	p,p'DDE	0.1031	2.2	
	PCB 28	0.0040	1.7	

Table 6. Cont.

Matrix	Compound	Percentile 75th	Threshold Value	Environmental Status per Compound	
Sediment (POPs and PAHs µg/kg dry weight; HMs µg/g dry weight)	PCB 52	0.2153	2.7	GES	
	PCB 101	0.0097	3		
	PCB 118	0.0204	0.6		
	PCB 153	0.0090	40		
	PCB 138	0.0070	7.9		
	PCB 180	0.0030	12		
	Naphthalene	3.1109	160	GES	
	Acenaphthene	0.100	16		
	Phenanthrene	36.3327	240		
	Anthracene	0.100	85		
	Fluoranthene	31.2204	600		
	Pyrene	15.8545	665		
	Benzo[a] anthracene	7.1434	261		
	Chrysene	4.0159	384		
	Benzo[a] pyrene	16.1312	430		
	Benzo(g,h,i) perylene	0.100	85		
	Indeno(1,2,3-c,d) pyrene	4.2325	240	GES	
	Total Σ HAP	177.9075	1000		
	Copper	39.75	40		GES
	Cadmium	0.28	1.2		
Lead	31.25	47			
Nickel	47.11	35	Non-GES		
Chromium	36.78	81	GES		

* The limit of detection (LoD) for heptachlor is higher than the threshold value stipulated by Directive 39/2013. The percentage refers to LoD exceedances. Green—GES achieved, red—GES not achieved.

Persistent Organic Pollutants (POPs)

The concentrations of most POPs in the marine waters of the shelf zone were high, exceeding the threshold values in 19–91% of the samples (Figure 5). Hexachlorobenzene (HCB) was the only compound that had a good ecological status. Consequently, the water assessment resulted in a poor ecological status due to the application of the OAO principle (Table 6). In sediments, all compounds had a good ecological status (75th percentile of data was below threshold).

Figure 5. Exceedances of the threshold values for OCPs in shelf marine waters, 2020–2022.

Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAHs)

The concentration of these pollutants in the shelf marine waters was low, with the 75th percentile values being below the threshold values and resulting in GES in both water and sediment. However, for fluoranthene, exceedances of the threshold values were observed in water in 14% of the samples. Overall, in this reporting unit, GES was achieved (Table 6).

Heavy Metals (HMs)

In water, all HMs have 75th percentile concentrations well below their respective Environmental Quality Standards (EQSs). Exceedances of EQSs were minimal, with copper (Cu) and cadmium (Cd) exceeding their EQSs in 2% of samples. The overall ecological status for all HMs in the water matrix is classified as Good Ecological Status (GES). In sediments, copper (Cu) is very close to its EQS, with a 75th percentile of 39.75 µg/g compared to the EQS of 40 µg/g. Although 25% of the samples exceeded the EQS, it remains within an acceptable limit, so the status for this element is classified as GES. Lead (Pb) and chromium (Cr) have low exceedance rates (5% and 1% respectively) and maintain a GES status. Nickel (Ni) is the most concerning, with a 75th percentile concentration of 47.11 µg/g, exceeding the EQS of 35 µg/g, and 54% of samples surpassing the EQS. This results in a nickel being classified as non-GES in the sediment matrix (Table 6).

However, as we mentioned for the transitional area, previous studies reported that the Ni concentrations in north-western Black Sea sediments consistently exceed the Effect Range Low (ERL) values [61]. These elevated Ni levels are primarily driven by natural geochemical processes, as indicated by the strong correlation with Fe₂O₃ and total organic carbon (TOC), reflecting the naturally high background concentrations of the region, rather than significant anthropogenic contamination [60–63]. Additional research is needed to better clarify the contributions of natural versus human-induced sources [64–67].

The integration of individual compound results within each contaminant group, following the OAO principle, revealed a mix of ecological statuses: some contaminant groups/matrices showed a poor ecological status, while others maintained a good ecological status. When the results for all contaminant groups and matrices were combined using the OAO principle, the overall environmental status for the shelf marine waters area was determined to be non-GES (Table 7).

Table 7. Status of shelf marine waters, 2020–2022.

MRU	Matrix	Group of Compounds	Environmental Status per Group of Contaminants	Environmental Status for MRU
Shelf marine waters BLK-RO-RG-MT01	Water	POPs	Non-GES	Non-GES
		PAHs	GES	
		HMs	GES	
	Sediment	POPs	GES	
		PAHs	GES	
		HMs	Non-GES	

Green—GES achieved, red—GES not achieved.

3.1.4. Offshore Waters (BLK_RO_RG_MT02)

The data presented in Table 8 are based on 18 seawater and 3 sediments samples collected between 2020 and 2022. Only POPs and PAHs were analyzed in sediments. The 75th percentile was calculated by sorting the seawater data and selecting the value below which 75% of the results fall, ensuring that natural variability is accounted for. GES is achieved when the 75th percentile is below the EQS, meaning that the exceedance rates are less than 25%. The percentage of samples exceeding threshold values (EQS or ERL) was calculated to assess the frequency of contamination above acceptable levels, providing insight into potential environmental risks.

Table 8. Status of the offshore waters, 2020–2022 (POPs, PAHs, HMs).

Matrix	Compound	Percentile 75th	Threshold Value	Environmental Status per Compound
Water ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	HCB	0.206	0.05	Non-GES
	Lindane	8.426	0.02	
	Heptachlor *	0.003	0.00003	GES
	Sum of cyclodiene pesticides	4.204	0.005	Non-GES
	p,p' DDT	0.940	0.01	
	DDT total	7.836	0.025	
	PCB 118	0.0004	0.6	
	PCB 153	0.0006	40	
	PCB 138	0.0030	7.9	
	PCB 180	0.0012	12	GES
	Naphthalene	0.0169	130	
	Anthracene	0.0001	0.1	
	Fluoranthene	0.0001	0.12	
	Benzo(a)pyrene	0.0001	0.027	
	Benzo(b)fluoranthene	0.0001	0.017	
	Benzo(k) fluoranthene	0.0001	0.017	
	Benzo(g,h,i)perylene	0.0001	0.00082	
	Copper	7.49	30	GES
	Cadmium	0.02	1.5	
	Lead	1.87	14	
Nickel	2.28	34		
Chromium	37.64	100		

* The limit of detection (LoD) for heptachlor is higher than the threshold value stipulated by Directive 39/2013. The percentage refers to LoD exceedances. Green—GES achieved, red—GES not achieved.

Persistent Organic Pollutants (POPs)

The concentrations of most POPs in offshore marine waters were high, surpassing the threshold values in 22% to 100% of the samples (Figure 6). Heptachlor was the sole compound that fulfilled the criteria for GES. Consequently, the water quality assessment resulted in a non-GES status (Table 8). In sediments, all compounds were below threshold values, resulting in a good overall environmental status for this matrix.

Figure 6. Exceedances of threshold values for OCPs in the offshore waters, 2020–2022.

Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAHs)

The concentrations of these compounds in the offshore waters zone were low, with the 75th percentile values being below the threshold values. Overall, in this reporting unit, GES was achieved (Table 8).

Heavy Metals (HMs)

The 75th percentile of copper (Cu) concentrations is 7.49 µg/L, well below the Environmental Quality Standard (EQS) of 30 µg/L. However, 7% of the samples exceeded the EQS. Because these exceedances are below 25%, the overall ecological status for copper is classified as good. The 75th percentile concentrations for Cd, Pb, Ni and Cr are all below their respective EQS values, with no exceedances reported. Consequently, each of these metals is classified as having a good status. Overall, the offshore marine waters show GES for all elements assessed (Table 8).

By combining the results for each element within contaminant groups, using the OOA principle, a poor ecological status was identified for certain groups of contaminants and matrices, while others maintained a good ecological status. Overall, applying the OOA principle to the combined results for all contaminant groups and matrices led to the offshore waters having a poor status (non-GES) (Table 9).

Table 9. Environmental status of offshore waters, 2020–2022.

MRU	Matrix	Group of Compounds	Ecological Status for Group of Contaminants	Ecological Status of MRU
Offshore marine waters BLK-RO-RG-MT02	Water	POPs	Non-GES	Non-GES
		PAHs	GES	
		HMs	GES	
	Sediment	POPs	GES	
		PAHs	GES	

Green—GES achieved, red—GES not achieved.

3.2. Descriptor 9: Contaminant Assessment in Seafood

The assessment of contaminants in commercially important mollusk species (*Rapana venosa* and *Mytilus galloprovincialis*) was carried out based on the analysis of data obtained in each reporting zone (coastal and marine) for every compound that has MACs for human consumption defined by national and European legislation [34,58], as follows: POPs—OCPs and the sum of six PCBs (PCB28, PCB52, PCB101, PCB138, PCB153 and PCB 180), PAHs—benzo(a)pyrene, and HMs—Cd and Pb. By comparing the measured concentrations to regulatory limits, this report assesses the ecological status of MRUs, using the 75th percentile as a benchmark to determine if the levels of these contaminants are within acceptable ranges for human consumption and environmental health (GES).

The data presented in Table 10; Table 11 are based on 18 mollusk samples collected between 2020 and 2022. The 75th percentile was calculated by sorting the data and selecting the value below which 75% of the results fall, ensuring that natural variability is accounted for. GES is achieved when the 75th percentile is below the EQS, meaning that the exceedance rates are less than 25%. The percentage of samples exceeding threshold values (EQS or ERL) was calculated to assess the frequency of contamination above acceptable levels, providing insight into potential environmental risks.

3.2.1. Coastal Waters—BLK-RO-RG-CT

Persistent Organic Pollutants (POPs)

The concentrations of most POPs in mollusk species (*Rapana venosa* and *Mytilus galloprovincialis*) from coastal waters were high, exceeding the threshold values in 44–78%

of samples. Hexachlorobenzene (HCB) and endrin were the only compounds that achieved GES (Table 10).

Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAHs)

The concentrations of benzo(a)pyrene in mollusk species (*Rapana venosa* and *Mytilus galloprovincialis*) from coastal waters were low, with no exceedances of the threshold value (Table 10).

Heavy Metals (HMs)

The concentrations of Cd and Pb in mollusk species were within acceptable limits for achieving GES (Table 10).

Table 10. Environmental status for POPs, PAHs and HMs in mollusk species from the coastal waters, 2020–2022.

Compound POPs and PAHs ($\mu\text{g/g ww}$); HMs ($\mu\text{g/g dw}$)	Percentile 75th	MAC	MAC Exceedances (%)	Environmental Status
HCB	0.005	0.02	0	GES
Lindane	0.192	0.1	67	Non-GES
Heptaclor	1.295	0.02	78	
Aldrin	0.129	0.02	56	
Dieldrin	0.711	0.2	67	
Endrin	0.0001	0.05	0	GES
DDT (sum of p,p'DDE, p,p'DDD, p,p'DDT)	5.867	0.01	78	Non-GES
Sum of 6 PCB (PCB 28, PCB 52, PCB 101, PCB 153, PCB 138, PCB 180)	0.139	0.075	44	
Benzo(a)pyrene	0.0001	10	0	GES
Cadmium (Cd)	1.282	5	0	GES
Lead (Pb)	0.122	7.5	0	GES

Green—GES achieved, red—GES not achieved.

3.2.2. Marine Waters Shelf Area—BLK-RO-RG-MT01

Persistent Organic Pollutants (POPs)

The concentrations of most POPs in mollusk species (*Rapana venosa* and *Mytilus galloprovincialis*) from shelf waters were high, exceeding the threshold values in 44–78% of samples. Aldrin was the only compound that achieved GES (Table 11).

Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAHs)

The concentrations of benzo(a)pyrene in mollusk species (*Rapana venosa* and *Mytilus galloprovincialis*) from shelf waters were low, with no exceedances of the threshold value (Table 11).

Heavy Metals (HMs)

The concentrations of Cd and Pb in the mollusk species from shelf waters were within acceptable limits for GES (Table 11).

Combining the results obtained for each compound within pollutant groups highlighted the GES achieved for some groups of contaminants and the non-GES status of others. By combining the results for all groups of contaminants according to the OAO principle, a poor status (non-GES) was determined for the two evaluation zones (Table 12).

Table 11. Environmental status for POPs, PAHs and HMs in mollusk species from the shelf waters, 2020–2022.

Compound POPs and PAHs ($\mu\text{g/g ww}$); HMs ($\mu\text{g/g dw}$)	Percentile 75th	MAC	MAC Exceedances (%)	Environmental Status
HCB	0.112	0.02	44	Non-GES
Lindane	0.551	0.1	56	
Heptaclor	0.443	0.02	78	
Aldrin	0.000045	0.02	0	GES
Dieldrin	0.366	0.2	44	Non-GES
Endrin	0.415	0.05	33	
DDT (sum of p,p'DDE, p,p'DDD, p,p'DDT)	1.625	0.01	78	
Sum of 6 PCB (PCB 28, PCB 52, PCB 101, PCB 153, PCB 138, PCB 180)	0.368	0.075	67	GES
Benzo(a)pyrene	0.0185	10	0	
Cadmium (Cd)	3.131	5	0	
Lead (Pb)	0.540	7.5	0	GES

Green—GES achieved, red—GES not achieved.

Table 12. Environmental status for coastal and shelf zones, 2020–2022.

MRU	Group of Compounds	Environmental Status for Each Group of Compounds	Environmental Status for the Evaluation Area
Coastal waters BLK_RO_RG_CT	POPs	Non-GES	Non-GES
	PAHs	GES	
	HMs	Non-GES	
Shelf waters BLK_RO_RG_MT01	POPs	Non-GES	Non-GES
	PAHs	GES	
	HMs	Non-GES	

Green—GES achieved, red—GES not achieved.

Our assessment of the contamination status (Descriptors 8 and 9) of the Romanian Black Sea waters covering a 3 year-period showed that no Marine Reporting Unit (MRU) achieved a good environmental status, following the OOA approach.

The One Out, All Out (OOAO) approach is a widely used method for environmental assessments, particularly in frameworks like the Water Framework Directive (WFD) and Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) [68]. One of its key advantages is that it acts as a precautionary tool, ensuring that even minor exceedances of individual contaminants are detected, thereby preventing potential cumulative or long-term environmental harm [69]. OOA simplifies decision-making by focusing on the worst-performing metric, making it easy to identify areas of concern. This makes it particularly effective in maintaining strict environmental standards and ensuring that ecosystems are protected from any possible deterioration [70].

However, the limitations of the OOA approach are significant [71,72]. It is often considered overly conservative, as it can classify an entire area as failing to achieve Good Environmental Status (GES) based on a single contaminant exceeding its threshold, even if other indicators show that the ecosystem is healthy. This rigid approach may lead to a skewed representation of the actual environmental status, as it ignores the variability in the impact of different contaminants [57]. Additionally, OOA does not account for the magnitude of the exceedance, as a small breach of a threshold may be treated the same as a severe one, leading to potentially disproportionate management responses [69]. As a result,

OOAO can produce fragmented assessments that focus on individual substances rather than the broader ecological context.

To overcome these limitations, OOAo should be combined with more integrated and weighted approaches that provide a fuller picture of environmental health [73]. Both the HELCOM Chemical Status Assessment Tool (CHASE) [74] and the Chemical Quality Index (CQI), used in Italy MSFD assessments [75], apply the OOAo principle, but in a more flexible, weighted manner. CHASE integrates data from various environmental matrices (water, sediment, biota) and multiple contaminants, offering a holistic assessment of chemical pollution by classifying regions as problem areas or non-problem areas based on the exceedances of agreed-upon thresholds [76]. Similarly, the CQI approach applies OOAo, but incorporates weighted hazard coefficients for different contaminants, prioritizing those with a greater ecological impact [75]. This weighted integration in both tools reduces the risk of overly rigid assessments, as it allows minor exceedances to be contextualized within the broader environmental picture.

In the Black Sea region, the CHASE tool was first tested within the ANEMONE project [77]. The promising results suggest that CHASE should be considered for future assessments in the region, which will enhance our understanding of the pollution status and effects, enabling more effective measures to protect the marine environment.

4. Discussion

Following the evaluation of the contamination of the Romanian marine ecosystem, based upon the MSFD methodology, the discussions will now address the detailed aspects of pollution spatial distribution, focusing on identifying the dominant compounds, understanding their spatial distribution in various areas, and investigating potential sources of contamination, such as rivers, wastewater treatment plants, maritime traffic and industrial discharges.

Frequent contaminants in the Black Sea region include POPs, HMs, PAHs, and excess nutrients [2,38,39,77,78]. PCBs and OCPs are particularly prevalent, linked to historical pesticide use and industrial chemicals. HMs, including lead, cadmium, and mercury, are also expected to be significant pollutants, largely attributed to industrial activities and legacy pollution. PAHs, which are often linked to petroleum products and combustion processes, are another category of pollutants that threaten the coastal ecosystem [26,79–83].

Identifying the potential sources of these contaminants is crucial for understanding their distribution along Romanian Black Sea sector and guiding future management efforts. One of the primary sources of both PAHs and POPs is petroleum-related activities [84], which have a long history in the region. Offshore oil and gas exploration and production continues to be a significant contributor to the contamination observed in both coastal and offshore waters [4]. Oil spills, operational discharges, and leaks during the extraction, transport, and processing of crude oil introduce PAHs directly into the marine environment [85]. This is further exacerbated by activities related to maritime transportation, including shipping lanes, oil tankers, and the three major Romanian ports—Constanța, Mangalia, and Midia [86]. These ports handle significant amounts of petroleum products, making them hotspots for petroleum-derived pollutants entering the marine system.

Another major source of PAHs is the combustion of fossil fuels, which releases these compounds into the atmosphere, where they can be transported over long distances and deposited into marine ecosystems [87]. Combustion processes related to maritime transport (e.g., ship emissions), industrial activities, and vehicular traffic in urbanized coastal areas all contribute to the PAH load [88]. Constanța, as one of the largest port cities in the region, sees significant combustion-related emissions from the increased shipping traffic and industrial activity, particularly in the petrochemical sector. The combustion of petroleum products, such as diesel and fuel oil, produces a complex mixture of PAHs, with high-molecular-weight PAHs (e.g., benzo[a]pyrene, chrysene) typically linked to pyrolytic processes [85]. These compounds are more likely to originate from high-temperature combustion, such as that in ship engines, industrial furnaces, and vehicle exhausts.

In addition to direct discharges, both PAHs and POPs can enter the marine environment via atmospheric deposition [89]. Combustion processes release these contaminants into the air, where they can bind to particulate matter and settle into the sea. This process is especially significant for POPs, which are highly persistent and can travel vast distances before being deposited in water bodies, contributing to both local and regional contamination [90].

Industrial activities and urban runoff are also key contributors to the presence of pollutants in the marine environment [91]. Urbanized areas along the coast could discharge untreated or insufficiently treated wastewater into the sea, particularly during periods of heavy rainfall. Wastewater treatment plants, while improved in recent years [4], still face challenges related to the effective removal of all contaminants. Urban runoff contains a variety of pollutants, including residues from petroleum products, heavy metals, and POPs, which enter the marine environment through riverine inputs and stormwater drainage systems [91].

POPs, including polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) and organochlorine pesticides (OCPs), have been widely used in agriculture and industry, and despite bans or restrictions on their use, they persist in the environment due to their stability and long half-lives [92]. Their presence is often linked to historical use as well as atmospheric transport from distant sources [93]. POPs are also introduced into the marine ecosystem through urban runoff, industrial discharges, and the improper disposal of hazardous waste [90].

The Danube River, as well as other major rivers such as the Dniester, Dnieper, Don, and Bug, serves as a significant transport route for pollutants from inland regions [17]. These rivers carry industrial waste, agricultural runoff (including pesticides), and urban pollutants directly into the Black Sea [26]. The Danube is a major source of contaminants due to the diverse land uses along its course through Europe, including extensive industrial and agricultural zones [94].

In particular, OCPs continue to impact the Black Sea due to legacy contamination from agricultural runoff, riverine inputs, wastewater discharges, and atmospheric deposition. Despite bans, residues persist in coastal and transitional waters, with rivers acting as a major source from upstream agricultural regions. Urban runoff and wastewater near coastal cities further contribute to this load, while atmospheric deposition enables long-range transport, highlighting the complex interplay of pollution sources.

4.1. Persistent Organic Pollutants (POPs)

Our study showed that among POPs, organochlorine pesticides (OCPs) represent the dominant compounds in the Romanian Black Sea sector, in both water and sediments, despite their restricted or banned status (Figure 7). This persistence can be attributed to their chemical stability, which allows them to resist environmental breakdown, and their ability to bioaccumulate in the tissues of organisms, leading to biomagnification throughout the food chain. Additionally, the global nature of marine currents facilitates the widespread distribution of these pollutants, contaminating marine environments far from their original sources. The continued presence of OCPs in marine environments has significant ecological and human health implications. These pollutants disrupt marine ecosystems by affecting their reproductive success, immune function, and overall health status. For humans, the consumption of seafood contaminated with OCPs poses health risks, including reproductive problems, developmental disorders, and cancer [95–99].

The persistence of these contaminants is further reinforced by historical usage, which has left a legacy of contamination in the environment, and their ability to bind to sediment particles, creating long-term reservoirs. Additionally, these compounds can be volatilized and transported over long distances through the atmosphere before being deposited in marine environments [100].

Sediments in transitional and coastal stations exhibit higher concentrations of OCPs, contrasting with the lower levels observed offshore. The data indicate that these areas experience the long-term accumulation of OCPs, likely due to the influence of local sources such as riverine input and industrial activities (Figure 8).

Figure 7. Percentage contribution of the average content of organochlorine pesticides (OCPs) and polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) in water (a) and sediments (b) from the Romanian Black Sea sector, 2020–2022.

Figure 8. Average content of organochlorine pesticides (OCPs) in waters ($\mu\text{g/L}$) and sediments ($\mu\text{g/g}$) from the Romanian section of the Black Sea, 2020–2022.

Notably, high concentrations of OCPs in the offshore water of the northern sector of the Romanian Black Sea (continental shelf) were observed. These elevated levels in water suggest recent contamination events, potentially from atmospheric deposition or intensified maritime traffic, as the sediments from the same offshore locations show relatively low OCPs concentrations (Figure 8). This discrepancy between water and sediment data indicates that these contaminants have not yet accumulated in the sediment, supporting the hypothesis of recent introduction rather than long-term persistence.

Atmospheric deposition may be a significant contributor to these high pesticide concentrations in the offshore waters where riverine and direct coastal inputs are less influential. The recent geopolitical situation, including increased maritime traffic due to grain transport toward Romanian ports, has further intensified anthropogenic pressure in these areas [101]. Additional influences such as the transportation of agricultural runoff via atmospheric processes cannot be ruled out. This spatial variation in OCP contamination, with elevated water concentrations and low sediment accumulation in the offshore area, highlights the complexity of pollutant dynamics in this region and underscores the need for the continuous monitoring of both water and sediment to capture short-term contamination events and their long-term ecological impact. Future investigations should focus on distinguishing between atmospheric inputs and maritime traffic contributions to better manage these pollution sources.

The geographical dispersion of PCBs in water shows the complex mixture of compounds to which Romanian transitional and coastal waters are exposed from various sources, including rivers, cities, and industries. Specifically, in these areas, a wide variety of PCB congeners is observed, reflecting the influence of both local and regional sources. As shown in Figure 9, PCB concentrations are higher near river mouths and urban and industrial areas. The occurrence of multiple prevalent PCB compounds suggests persistent contamination, likely from historical uses and legacy pollution associated with these pollutants. In the open marine waters, the PCB contamination pattern becomes simpler, with PCB52 dominating the mixture (Figure 9). PCB52, being a lighter and smaller molecule, is more easily transported via atmospheric pathways, which explains its widespread distribution across more distant marine areas [102]. This highlights atmospheric deposition as a key mechanism influencing PCB contamination in offshore waters, especially for lighter congeners like PCB52.

Similarly, in sediments, PCB distribution patterns are shaped by both riverine inputs and industrial activities. Figure 10 highlights the prevalence of heavier PCB congeners, such as PCB28 and PCB118, in transitional and coastal sediments, indicating localized contamination likely associated with industrial and urban sources. In the northern part of the open marine zone, higher concentrations of PCB28 and PCB118 are also observed, while lighter congeners like PCB52 are more dominant in the southern areas (Figure 10). This distribution suggests varying contamination pathways, with point sources such as industrial activity and river discharge impacting the northern coastline, while atmospheric transport and diffuse pollution are more prominent in the southern open marine region.

The spatial variation in PCB contamination across the Romanian coastal and marine waters demonstrates the combined effects of both localized and regional sources. Riverine inputs, atmospheric deposition, and maritime activities all contribute to this complex pollution pattern. Future monitoring efforts should focus on distinguishing these sources more clearly to inform targeted management strategies.

Figure 9. Percentage contribution of individual compounds to the average content of polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) in water, 2020–2022.

Figure 10. Percentage contribution of individual compounds to the average content of polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) in sediments, 2020–2022.

4.2. Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAHs)

PAHs showed heterogeneous values, highlighting the contribution of river input and anthropogenic sources, particularly in the Constanța Port area (Figure 11). Constanța, as a major hub for maritime transport and industrial activities [86], experiences significant PAH inputs from shipping traffic, which has recently seen a substantial increase due to the ongoing regional conflict and disruptions in traditional shipping routes. This surge in maritime traffic, particularly with vessels rerouted to Romanian ports, has intensified emissions from fuel combustion and cargo handling, further contributing to the PAH load in the area. Petroleum-related activities, including oil refineries, the shipping of petroleum products, and bunkering operations, remain major contributors to PAH emissions. These activities release various PAHs, such as pyrene, fluoranthene, and benzo(a)pyrene, which are common indicators of the combustion processes associated with fossil fuels.

Figure 11. Total content of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) in waters ($\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$) and sediments ($\mu\text{g}/\text{g}$), 2020–2022.

In addition to the main port, the two satellite ports of Constanța—Midia, located 25 km to the north, and Mangalia, 38 km to the south—also play significant roles in the region’s maritime industry [86]. Midia specializes in oil and gas operations, further intensifying the local PAH load, while Mangalia, a shipyard and commercial port, adds to the pollution through shipbuilding and repair activities. Both satellite ports, together with Constanța, contribute to the release of petroleum-derived PAHs into the marine environment. Petroleum terminals, routine discharges, accidental spills, and the handling of large quantities of petroleum products across these ports contribute substantially to PAH contamination [103]. Elevated concentrations of PAHs, such as chrysene and benzo(a)anthracene, in water and sediment samples near the Constanța complex indicate significant local pollution. Additionally, atmospheric deposition from combustion sources in the port areas exacerbates the spread of these contaminants.

The extent of PAH contamination across Constanța and its satellite ports suggests that local sources, particularly petroleum activities, are primary contributors to the overall pollution load. The PAHs from these anthropogenic activities not only affect local marine

ecosystems but may also be transported to adjacent coastal areas and further offshore by currents, as reflected by the elevated levels detected in open marine waters.

Our data showed that anthracene and phenanthrene are the predominant PAHs introduced into the Danube–Black Sea transition zone [104], especially in front of the Sulina and Sf. Gheorghe branches, up to the 30 m isobath. In contrast, the offshore marine waters in the northern region are primarily characterized by the presence of fluorene and fluoranthene. The coastal anthropogenic influence is marked by a more complex PAH mixture, with phenanthrene and anthracene being the predominant components. The areas adjacent to petroleum activities (the Petromidia refinery and OMV platforms) are characterized by the presence of pyrene and, to some extent, fluorene. Notably, naphthalene is present in the southern shelf waters, while naphthalene and fluorene are almost exclusively found in the offshore zone. The maximum value observed was solely due to the presence of chrysene and benzo(a)anthracene at the 60 m isobath in the Mangalia area (Figure 12).

Figure 12. Percentage contribution of individual compounds to the average content of PAHs in seawater ($\mu\text{g/L}$), 2020–2022.

The sources of PAHs could include both natural (petrogenic/biogenic) and anthropogenic (pyrolytic) origins [105]. Our observations suggest influences from both fossil fuel combustion, as well as direct petrogenic contributions. However, certain areas exhibit a clear anthropogenic influence characterized by a predominance of pyrolytic PAHs, such as the Gura Buhaz profile near the Petromidia refinery and the Midia port, the Constanța and Mangalia port areas, and the northern shelf waters, specifically in the 70–200 m bathymetric strip. Conversely, the southern shelf and offshore waters are dominated by petrogenic PAHs (Figure 13).

Sediments near the mouth of the Danube show the significant accumulation of pyrolytic PAHs, with phenanthrene, fluoranthene, and benzo(a)pyrene being the primary compounds. The anthropogenic influence of the petroleum terminal and the Midia and Constanța ports is also reflected in the presence of petrogenic PAHs. In contrast, sediments

in the southern sector are almost exclusively polluted with pyrolytic hydrocarbons, such as phenanthrene and benzo(a)pyrene. Additionally, the influence of pyrolytic PAHs is evident in the offshore marine sediments (Figures 14 and 15).

Figure 13. Percentage contribution of petrogenic/biogenic and pyrolytic hydrocarbons to the average content of PAHs in the waters (µg/L), 2020–2022.

Figure 14. Percentage contribution of individual compounds to the average content of PAHs in sediments (µg/g), 2020–2022.

Figure 15. Percentage contribution of petrogenic/biogenic and pyrolytic hydrocarbons to the average content of PAHs in sediments ($\mu\text{g/g}$), 2020–2022.

4.3. Heavy Metals (HMs)

HMs pollution in marine environments is a significant concern due to its detrimental effects on both ecological and human health. The sources of HMs can be categorized as natural and anthropogenic origins. Natural sources primarily include geological processes such as the weathering of metal-bearing rocks and volcanic eruptions, which contribute trace amounts of the metals essential for marine life [106,107]. However, anthropogenic activities have increasingly overshadowed these natural contributions, leading to elevated levels of HMs in coastal waters and sediments. Major anthropogenic sources include industrial discharges, agricultural runoff, urban wastewater, and mining activities [108–111].

The impact of HM pollution is particularly pronounced in coastal areas, where human activities are concentrated. For instance, studies have shown that HMs such as cadmium (Cd), lead (Pb), and mercury (Hg) are often found in high concentrations in sediments and seawater near industrial zones and urban [112–114].

The bioaccumulation of HMs in marine organisms poses additional risks to human health. Fish and shellfish, which are vital components of the human diet, can accumulate harmful levels of metals, leading to potential health risks upon consumption [115–117]. The toxicity of HMs can affect various organs, including the liver and kidneys, and can lead to long-term health issues [117,118]. Furthermore, the persistence of HMs in the environment complicates remediation efforts, as these pollutants can remain in ecosystems for extended periods, continually affecting marine life and human health [119,120].

The concentrations of HMs in Romanian marine waters, determined during 2020–2022, showed a high degree of variability. The copper distribution in surface waters reflects the influence of the Danube on transitional waters, as well as contributions from other remote sources, indicated by some elevated (extreme) values in the shelf and offshore marine waters of the northern sector. Conversely, the offshore waters in the southern sector show significantly lower values compared to coastal waters, particularly those near port areas. Cadmium exhibits a pronounced gradient from transitional and coastal waters to shelf and offshore marine waters. Higher lead concentrations were noted in coastal waters, likely

correlated with port activities, shipping, and wastewater treatment facilities, with these values significantly reduced in offshore marine waters. Nickel, similar to copper, shows a marked concentration gradient from north to south. In contrast, chromium displays a different distribution pattern from the other elements, with higher concentrations in offshore marine waters, implying that other sources, such as atmospheric deposition, could be contributing to these elevated levels (Figure 16).

Figure 16. Distribution of HMs in surface marine waters, 2020–2022.

In sediments, the distribution of HMs reveals notable spatial variability, influenced by both natural factors, such as grain size and the organic matter content, [121] and human activities, including industrial discharges, port operations, and riverine inputs. The ob-

served patterns suggest that areas with finer grain sizes and a higher organic content serve as repositories for HMs, as these characteristics facilitate the binding and accumulation of contaminants. The transitional and marine zones of the Romanian Black Sea sector display consistently higher concentrations of HMs, particularly in areas influenced by the Danube River. This is evident from the spatial distribution patterns (Figure 17), where sediments from the northern sector exhibits elevated levels of heavy metals. These areas are characterized by fine-grained sediments, which have a greater surface area for metal adsorption, and a higher organic matter content that enhances metal binding [60,121]. The Danube's extensive catchment area, which passes through industrialized and agricultural regions, contributes to the elevated HM levels, particularly for copper, cadmium, and lead, which are commonly associated with both natural and anthropogenic sources.

Figure 17. Concentrations of HMs in sediments, 2020–2022.

Localized peaks in HM concentrations are observed in coastal areas near major ports, such as Constanța and Mangalia. This is particularly noticeable for cadmium and nickel, which show distinct spatial patterns. Cadmium concentrations are significantly elevated near the Constanța port (Figure 17). This can be attributed to industrial discharges and urban runoff, compounded by the presence of wastewater treatment plants in the vicinity. Ports often act as a focal point for pollution due to their proximity to high-density urban areas and the heavy maritime traffic, which can introduce pollutants into the sediment through various means, including fuel combustion, metal corrosion, and accidental spills. Nickel concentrations are notably higher in port areas, particularly near Constanța and Mangalia (Figure 17), reflecting the influence of port operations, which may include activities such as metal handling, shipbuilding, and industrial emissions. Chromium shows a relatively uniform distribution across coastal and shelf sediments, with higher concentrations in transitional waters (Figure 17). This suggests multiple sources of Cr, including riverine inputs from the Danube and atmospheric deposition. While riverine inputs play a major role in transitional areas, the widespread presence of Cr in coastal zones points to long-range transport through atmospheric pathways and diffuse industrial emissions. Cr's strong affinity for fine particles and organic matter helps it persist and accumulate in these sediments over time.

The analysis of boxplots representing HM variability across different Marine Reporting Units (MRUs) (median values, interquartile ranges, and outliers) supports the interpretation of distribution maps and offers deeper insights into how contamination levels vary spatially, particularly highlighting the influence of riverine inputs and port activities (Figure 18). For instance, clear contamination gradients for most elements, with higher concentrations in transitional areas, or localized outliers near major ports, were confirmed (Figure 18). In particular, copper, nickel, and lead show the highest concentrations and variability in transitional waters, with significant outliers also seen in shelf waters, whereas cadmium shows outliers and higher concentrations in coastal and shelf waters. Chromium exhibits a more uniform distribution across the MRUs, but with higher concentrations and variability in transitional waters, indicated by several outliers (Figure 18).

A limitation of this study is the lack of data on the sediment organic carbon content and granulometry, which are important factors in understanding the mechanisms behind heavy metal accumulation. For the purpose of this paper, we relied on literature data to provide context for the observed spatial distribution patterns [122–128]. Incorporating direct measurements of these parameters would provide a more comprehensive explanation of the HMs distribution in Romanian Black Sea sediments. Future research should focus on analyzing the grain size distribution and organic matter content to gain a deeper understanding of the processes driving heavy metal deposition and accumulation in this region.

Previous research on Black Sea pollution has emphasized the substantial issue of contaminant distribution in the region. These studies have revealed that various factors, including hydrodynamic processes, riverine inputs, atmospheric deposition, sediment dynamics, and biological processes [129], influence the spatial distribution of pollutants. For instance, various studies have revealed concerning levels of HMs, particularly in areas influenced by river runoff and urban discharges [14–16]. Furthermore, the presence of PAHs, often resulting from industrial activities and oil spills, has been documented in the region, contributing to the degradation of marine ecosystems [17,18].

PCBs and OCPs have also been identified as significant contaminants. These compounds are known for their resistance to degradation, their capacity to build up within the food chain and their prolonged negative impacts on ecosystems [20,21]. Research has shown that the concentrations of pollutants in the Black Sea are affected by multiple factors, such as water dynamics and human activities, particularly from riverine inputs. A recent study identified over 80 types of organic pollutants in Black Sea waters, highlighting the extensive contamination faced by this semi-closed marine environment [19].

Figure 18. HM variability in sediments across different Marine Reporting Units (MRUs).

Our findings are consistent with earlier studies, showing that the spatial distribution of pollutants in the Black Sea area is shaped by several factors. Coastal areas near urban centers, industrial zones, and agricultural regions often exhibit higher pollution levels due to direct discharges and runoff [38,130]. Big rivers like the Danube, Dnieper, Don, Dniester, and Kızılırmak transport pollutants from inland sources, significantly impacting coastal waters during periods of high flow [78,131]. The pollution dynamics are further influenced by the Black Sea's cyclonic circulation system, which connects the waters of neighboring countries [132]. This current facilitates the redistribution of pollutants, transporting contaminants across national borders and affecting the entire northwestern and western sectors

of the Black Sea [133]. Hydrodynamic patterns in this system [134] emphasize the need for coordinated international efforts in pollution management and monitoring.

Sediment accumulation can also affect benthic organisms and potentially release contaminants back into the water column [135–137]. Sedimentation rates influence the dynamics of pollution. A notably high sedimentation rate in proximity to the Danube River delta has been observed, potentially resulting in the accumulation of pollutants within the sediments [138]. The bioaccumulation of hazardous substances in marine organisms poses a significant threat to both ecosystem and human health, necessitating robust monitoring and regulatory frameworks [28,37,139,140].

For the Romanian waters, the Danube River acts as a conduit for pollutants originating from upstream sources, including industrial activities, agricultural runoff, and urban wastewater. Ineffective wastewater treatment processes can lead to the release of pollutants into the marine ecosystem [141]. Industrial discharges, both coastal and inland, further contribute to the pollutant load [4]. Additionally, airborne pollutants introduced through atmospheric deposition affect both surface waters and sediments [142]. Also, the recent intensification of maritime traffic, due to the current regional geopolitical context, including ships transporting grains to Romanian ports, could represent an additional anthropogenic pressure upon the marine environment [101].

Overall, our study highlights the river's influence on Romanian Black Sea transitional waters across various matrices, namely, surface waters, sediments, and biota, affecting a wide range of pollutants. HMs concentrations, including nickel, lead, copper, and cadmium, show a clear decreasing spatial gradient from river mouths toward offshore areas or the south (Figures 16–18). Compounds such as DDT and its breakdown products, along with specific PCB congeners, are detected at elevated concentrations near the river's discharge zone (Figures 8 and 9). Among PAHs, compounds like anthracene showed localized exceedances in transitional waters (Figure 12).

Previous assessments found that transitional waters under the influence of the Danube often do not achieve GES, not only for contamination, but also for the eutrophication or biodiversity descriptors [2,12,29]. A regional study involving Ukraine, Romania, Bulgaria and Turkey that evaluated the influence of rivers on the Black Sea underscored the crucial role of rivers, including the Danube, as major conduits for pollutants such as HMs, POPs, and nutrients. A notable spatial gradient emerges, with the highest pollution concentrations occurring near river mouths, especially in the northwestern Black Sea, and decreasing offshore [78]. These findings emphasize the importance of sustained monitoring and cooperative regional management to reduce the impact of river-borne pollution on the Black Sea ecosystem.

The pollution dynamics in the Black Sea are compounded by the complex interplay of various sources, including atmospheric deposition, riverine inputs, and maritime and industrial activities [143–145]. A significant contributor to the degradation of the Black Sea ecosystem is nutrient pollution, primarily originating from agricultural runoff, wastewater treatment plants, and riverine discharges [146–148]. Excessive nutrient loads, especially nitrogen and phosphorus, lead to eutrophication, resulting in harmful algal blooms, hypoxia, and biodiversity loss, which further stress the marine environment [39]. The impacts of nutrient pollution are most evident in coastal and transitional waters, where agricultural and urban activities dominate [2]. Moreover, the cumulative effects of tourism, agriculture, and fishing activities further complicate the pollution landscape, necessitating a coordinated international response to mitigate these challenges [26,149].

In addressing the overall marine environmental quality of the Romanian Black Sea, our study aligns with key regional assessments, such as the Black Sea Commission (BSC) State of Environment Report [1], or the ANEMONE [38,77,78] and EMBLAS [149,150] Projects. These initiatives have consistently underscored the environmental challenges the Black Sea faces, particularly with eutrophication, pollution, biodiversity loss, and ecosystem degradation. The findings of our study contribute to the understanding of these persistent issues, offering updated insights specific to the Romanian sector and its progress toward

achieving GES, as required by the MSFD. It is important to note that only two Black Sea countries, Romania and Bulgaria, are EU members and thus required to meet GES targets under the MSFD, while other countries in the region are not bound by the same regulations. This creates additional complexity in managing the shared marine environment. Our study emphasizes the importance of enhancing cross-border cooperation for sustained monitoring, as highlighted in the ANEMONE [48] and EMBLAS projects, to effectively address these regional challenges and move toward a healthier and more sustainable Black Sea ecosystem.

While this study primarily focuses on surface waters and surface sediments, future research should investigate the variability in contaminants with depth, both in sediments and along the water column. Contaminant concentrations can vary significantly with sediment depth, particularly in areas influenced by riverine sedimentation. Deeper sediment layers may reveal long-term deposition trends, while resuspension events, due to natural hydrodynamics or human activities like dredging, could redistribute contaminants into the water column. Understanding the vertical distribution of contaminants in both sediments and the water column would provide a more comprehensive view of their long-term environmental impact. Additionally, future studies should further explore the influence of the Danube River, given its pivotal role in transporting pollutants into the Romanian Black Sea sector. Investigating seasonal variations in river discharge and their impact on contaminant levels, coupled with a focus on human activities contributing to riverine pollution, would enhance our understanding of the river's overall contribution to regional contamination patterns.

5. Conclusions

This study offers a critical evaluation of pollution levels in the Romanian Black Sea, focusing on water, sediment, and biota contamination. Key pollutants such as HMs, PAHs, and POPs were found to exceed regulatory thresholds, particularly near pollution hotspots. The findings highlight the need for enhanced regulations, regional cooperation, and better waste management to mitigate ongoing pollution challenges, including offshore contamination. By providing new data, especially for offshore areas, and advocating for improved multi-metric assessment tools, this study significantly contributes to future Good Environmental Status (GES) evaluations and marine pollution management under the MSFD framework.

The comprehensive assessment of the contamination status in the Romanian Black Sea ecosystem highlights significant environmental challenges that remain unresolved. Our findings indicate that none of the Marine Reporting Units (MRUs) achieved GES under the MSFD, demonstrating persistent contamination across all matrices—water, sediment, and biota. Critical pollutants, like HMs, POPs, and PAHs, remain a substantial risk for the health of marine ecosystems. The spatial distribution of pollutants underscores the need for targeted pollution control efforts, particularly in regions impacted by riverine inputs, industrial discharges, and urban runoff. The presence of contaminants even in offshore waters further indicates that diffuse sources, such as atmospheric deposition and increased maritime activity, are contributing to the overall pollution burden [101].

While the use of the “one out-all out” (OOAO) approach provided a sound framework for assessing GES, the complexity of marine pollution calls for more advanced methods [57,73]. By focusing on cumulative impacts rather than isolated exceedances, multi-metric, indicator-based methods, like the Chemical Status Assessment Tool (CHASE) [74,76] and Chemical Quality Index (CQI) [75], offer a more nuanced and adaptive framework for assessing chemical status. This integrated approach makes them more useful for decision-makers, as they better identify contamination hotspots and support targeted environmental management actions [76]. In future national assessments, we strongly recommend exploring the use of these tools, as they provide a more balanced and realistic evaluation of environmental status compared to traditional OOAO [57], allowing for better-informed and more effective marine protection measures.

Based on the study's findings and common environmental management practices, the following strategies to address the problem of pollution are proposed:

1. **Enhanced regional cooperation**
Given the transboundary nature of pollution in the Black Sea, fostering stronger regional cooperation among bordering nations is critical. This can include:
 - **Joint monitoring programs:** regular joint monitoring initiatives can help track pollution sources and trends.
 - **Shared data platforms:** developing a regional data-sharing platform to facilitate the exchange of environmental data can improve understanding and allow for coordinated response measures.
2. **Implementation of advanced pollution control technologies [151–153]**
To mitigate industrial discharges and agricultural runoffs, the following technologies can be recommended:
 - **Green infrastructure:** the construction of wetlands, riparian buffers, and bioreactors can help filter pollutants like nitrates, phosphates, and heavy metals before they reach coastal waters [154].
 - **Advanced wastewater treatment [155]:** upgrading existing wastewater treatment facilities to include technologies like membrane filtration, adsorption, or advanced oxidation processes could significantly reduce contaminant loads, particularly POPs and PAHs.
3. **Stricter enforcement of existing regulations**
 - **Tightening emission limits:** the stricter enforcement of existing pollution control measures, especially for industries and agricultural sectors, is essential. This could involve fines for non-compliance and incentives for industries that adopt cleaner technologies [156].
 - **Marine traffic management:** given the impact of maritime traffic on the pollution levels (especially PAHs from oil transport), implementing stricter pollution control regulations for vessels and promoting cleaner fuel alternatives for ships can help reduce pollution from this source [157,158].
4. **Integrated pollution assessment tools**
 - **Expanding the use of integrated multi-metric tools,** like the Chemical Status Assessment Tool (CHASE) and the Chemical Quality Index (CQI), which are used in other EU countries and which consider cumulative impacts rather than isolated pollutant exceedances [75,76,159,160]. This approach can provide more comprehensive environmental assessments and guide more effective management actions [161,162].
5. **Public and stakeholder engagement [163]**
 - **Community awareness campaigns:** raising awareness among local communities and stakeholders (e.g., industries, farmers, fishermen) regarding pollution sources and prevention strategies can foster greater compliance and promote sustainable practices.
 - **Incentive programs for cleaner practices:** offering incentives to industries or agricultural entities that adopt greener technologies or practices can encourage pollution reduction at the source [156].

Thus, to address the pressing issue of pollution in the region, it is imperative to strengthen regulatory frameworks, enhance monitoring and assessment capabilities, foster regional cooperation, and actively engage the public and stakeholders. The stricter enforcement of pollution control regulations, particularly for industrial and urban sources of contamination, is urgently needed. Expanding long-term monitoring programs to cover a wider range of contaminants and matrices, along with the adoption of more sophisticated assessment tools, will provide a more accurate understanding of contamination trends. Given the shared nature of the Black Sea, coordinated efforts between bordering nations

are essential for developing and implementing region-wide strategies to reduce pollution. Raising awareness about the impacts of marine contamination and involving local stakeholders in environmental management can foster greater compliance with pollution control measures and promote sustainable practices. By implementing these recommendations, we can work towards a healthier and more resilient Black Sea ecosystem.

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